

Exploring academic motherhood in mathematics education

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In this project presentation we describe an ongoing inquiry into the lived experiences of Academic Mothers in Mathematics Education (AM-ME) and the unique insights AM-ME gain while parenting, educating, and doing mathematics with their school-aged children. We focus on the rationale and significance for this inquiry and provide an overview of our project. During our session we will also discuss findings from a collaborative self-study, currently underway, that is part of our larger project on academic motherhood in mathematics education.

Rationale and significance

The ‘academic gender gap’ persists and disproportionately affects women with children (e.g., Huang et al., 2020; Thun, 2020) especially those who had children early in their career (e.g., Antecol et al., 2018; Mason et al., 2013). Women who are successful in combining full-time academic work with motherhood continue to face challenges in terms of working hours, stress levels, and work/family conflict, risking long-term health issues in the process (Ollianen, 2019). This reflects an historical bias against motherhood in academia, which has remained persistent despite more visibility of female faculty mothers (Mirick & Wladkowski, 2018), and has promoted a culture of silence around issues of academic motherhood (Pasque, 2015).

As we continue to live through a pandemic, during which inequities across the board are exacerbated, academic mothers may be the ones affected most in higher education institutions (Hermann & Neale-McFall, 2020) and risk suffering yet another ‘motherhood penalty’ (e.g., Baker 2012), as evident in journal submission data (e.g., Murdie, 2020; Staniskuaski, 2020), anecdotal reports from peers, and our own experiences as academic mothers of young children. Although academic fathers are not immune to the impacts of the pandemic, academic mothers have taken a greater hit (Langin, 2021). During the pandemic, academic mothers whose expertise lies in PK-12 education in particular became the default ‘teacher’ at home and continue to spend a significant amount of time supporting their children’s remote education, while focusing their academic work on serving their students and academic programs, rather than conducting research. In this way, the ‘invisible work’

Please cite as: Vomvoridi-Ivanovic, E., Ward, J., & Ingen Lauer, S. v. (2021). Exploring academic motherhood in mathematics education. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 239–242). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5393057>

that affects both the career advancement and overall well-being of academic mothers, has exponentially increased during the pandemic (Minello, 2020).

Working closely with their school-aged children during the pandemic, however, AM-ME in particular have been gaining unique insights into mathematics teaching and learning and are reimagining educational opportunities during this time of crisis (Vomvoridi-Ivanovic & Ward, 2021). This has positioned us and other AM-ME with school-aged children to become immersed in the teaching and learning of mathematics and draw expertise from mathematics education in novel ways. However, we find that it is these AM-ME who are less likely to find the time and energy to disseminate these insights to the broader mathematics education community. Further, AM-ME may not even consider these insights worthy of dissemination since doing mathematics with our children, and learning from this activity, is not typically considered publishable work. We are concerned that unique AM-ME insights that may contribute to advancing mathematics education will remain invisible, just like much of the ‘invisible work’ (Ahn et al., 2017) academic mothers do at home (Offer, 2014) and in the workplace (Guarino & Borden, 2017).

Project overview

Our project seeks to generate a content-specific counternarrative to the existing ‘narrative of constraint’ (Ward and Wolf-Wendel, 2012, p. 28) of what it means to be an academic mother in mathematics education by exploring AMs’-ME lived experiences during the pandemic and beyond, and identifying and naming the unique and multiple insights AM-ME bring to the professoriate while parenting, educating, and doing mathematics with their school-aged children. Our goal is to shift the discourse around academic motherhood to one that recognizes motherhood as an asset, rather than a deficit, through disseminating AMs’-ME unique contributions in mathematics (teacher) education scholarship.

Drawing on gendered views of work (e.g., Valian, 2005), post-structural feminism (Weedon, 1997), relational cultural theory (Miller & Stiver, 1997), and a funds of knowledge conceptual framework (e.g., Gonzalez & Moll, 2002), we seek to address the following overarching research questions: In what ways do AM-ME describe successes and challenges navigating their roles as academics, mothers, and mathematics (teacher) educators, during the COVID-19 pandemic and beyond? In what ways do these mothers perceive bi-directional influence between their roles? Subsections include:

1. What are the sources of these successes and challenges and how do AM-ME cope with the latter?
2. What are the funds of knowledge AM-ME with school-aged children gain while parenting, educating, and doing mathematics with their children, and in what ways do these funds of knowledge inform their work in the field of mathematics education and the teaching and learning of mathematics more broadly?

We, the three participant-authors in this study, are all academic mothers in mathematics education in the US. We have 7 children among us whose ages range from 4 to 14. In this

session we will discuss findings from a collaborative self-study, currently underway, whose purpose is to address the above questions as well as pilot data collection procedures for our larger project on academic motherhood in mathematics education. Our use of a collaborative self-study is purposeful in that we are aiming to focus on the nature of our work being self-initiated, improvement-aimed, interactive, inclusive of qualitative data, and trustworthy (LaBoskey, 2004). With our shared positions as AM-ME, we aim to guide each other towards sharing both our personal and professional growth and the ways in which we navigate our roles. It is from our collaboration that we begin to identify and illuminate our experiences in ways that we would not be able to individually (Baskerville & Goldblatt, 2009).

We engaged in narrative interviews (Jovchelovitch & Bauer, 2000), interviewed each other twice and offered probing questions until sufficient details were obtained, and transcribed each interview. Given the exploratory nature of the study, we used the principles of grounded theory to guide our coding and data analysis (Corbin & Strauss, 2015). We holistically read the interview transcripts and identified broad themes and categories. Then we used a combination of open coding and a-priori codes based on the lenses of our theoretical framework (Poststructural Feminism / Relational Cultural Theory / Funds of Knowledge). We engaged in multiple rounds of discussion about the codes. We used thematic analysis to identify, organize, and provide insight into the shared meanings and experiences of the participants (Braun & Clarke, 2012). Through the data analysis process, we named the specific funds of knowledge that we identified as leveraging across our roles as academics and mothers.

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